

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF CHRONIC RHINITIS (PRATISHYAYA): A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The disease in which the kaphadi dosas get dragged towards vayu & are expelled out through the nostrils is called pratishyaya. In Ayurveda, pratishyaya can be correlated with chronic simple rhinitis.^[1] Rhinitis is the inflammation of the nasal mucous membrane, & recurrent attacks of acute rhinitis lead to chronic rhinitis. Common symptoms are postnasal drip, nasal blockage, anosmia, headache, etc.^[2] The present case study provides the ayurvedic management of kaphaja pratishyaya using shamana aushadhi and nasya karma, along with slight dietary and lifestyle modifications. The treatment protocol focuses on dosha assessment and restoring digestive fire (agni). This ayurvedic line of treatment proved to be effective, with the patient remaining asymptomatic at three months of follow-up, which supports the efficacy of ayurvedic

management for kaphaja pratishyaya (chronic rhinitis).

KEYWORDS: Kaphaja Pratishyaya, Chronic Rhinitis, Case Study, Nasya.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic rhinitis (CR) is defined as an inflammation of the nasal mucosa, characterized by two or more symptoms of nasal congestion, rhinorrhea, sneezing, and itching for at least 1 hour daily and for more than 2 weeks.^[3] In Ayurveda, the word “Pratishyaya” is derived from “shyeng gatau” dhatu and “prati” upsarg, which means continuous movement of doshas.^[4] Pratishyaya is described under nasagata rogas and is of five types. ‘Nasa hi

shirsodwaram',^[5] according to Ayurveda, the nose is considered the gateway of the head and medicine administered through the nose provides strength to the structures above the neck. Kaphaja pratishyaya is one of the five types of pratishyaya.^[6] The vitiated vata, pitta, and kapha, together with rakta or separately, get localized in shira or gharanamula due to various etiological factors like exposure to fog, smoke, dust, daytime sleeping, awakening at night, etc. Further aggravation of vayu is induced by the previously stagnant dosha in shira as well as the continuation of an unwholesome diet & habits. This severely aggravated vayu drags the kaphadi doshas towards the nostril & thus precipitates pratishyaya. The prodromal symptoms of Kaphaja Pratishyaya (Chronic Simple Rhinitis) are a feeling of heaviness in the head, face & body; excessive itching in the head, throat, lips, palate & nose; dyspnea; vomiting; sweetness in the mouth; repeated whitish cold; sticky nasal discharge; etc. As per Maharshi Kasyapa, this vyadhi is chronic in nature & it is a sadhya vyadhi.^[7]

CASE REPORT

Patient information

A 38-year-old male visited the Shalakyantra OPD of RGMACH, Belley Shankarpur, West Bengal, with complaints of sneezing, runny nose, headache, heaviness of head and fever for 2 years.

- **Name:** xxxxxxxx
- **Age:** 38 years
- **Sex:** male
- **Religion:** Hindu
- **Occupation:** accountant
- **Marital status:** married
- **Socio-economic status:** middle class

Chief complaints

- Nasal congestion for 2 years
- Frequent sneezing and rhinorrhea (6–10 episodes/day)
- Postnasal drip with throat irritation
- Heaviness in the head
- Headache
- Fever

History of present illness

The patient reported intermittent nasal symptoms for 2 years, with seasonal exacerbations and triggers such as dust exposure. The patient was taking allopathic treatments, but they offered only temporary relief.

Personal history

Diet: Diet predominantly included cold, heavy, and stale foods, with curd at night.

Sleep- Disturbed

Appetite: Low

Thirst: Moderate

Bowel- Regular

Micturition: Normal

Kostha: Madhyama

Akriti: Madhyam

Vitals history

- **Blood Pressure:** 122/82 mm of hg.
- **Pulse:** 78/min.
- **Temperature:** 100 °f
- **Respiratory Rate:** 18/min.

Examination

- **General:** Fairly built
- **Local:** Pale, edematous nasal mucosa with watery discharge
- **Prakriti:** Vata-kaphaja
- **Nidana:** Atisheeta bhojana, ratri jagarana, raja-sevana (dust exposure).

Diagnosis: Kaphaja Pratishyaya (chronic simple rhinitis).

Treatment plan**1. Shodhana chikitsa**

- Nasya with anu taila, 5 drops per nostril for 14 days.

2. Shamana chikitsa

- Haridra khanda 3g twice daily with warm milk
- Sirahsuladi vajra rasa, 2 tablets bdpc with lukewarm water

- Vyosadi vati, 2 tablets bdpc with lukewarm water
- Trikatu churna, 1–2g with lukewarm water bdpc

Pathya–apathya (diet & lifestyle)

- Avoid cold, oily, heavy, stale foods and curd at night.
- Encourage regular intake of lukewarm water and light, easily digestible food.
- Advise anuloma-viloma (pranayama) and steam inhalation.
- Patient was advised to wear a mask to avoid dust.

DISCUSSION

This case study illustrates the successful treatment of Kaphaja Pratishyaya (Chronic Simple Rhinitis) through an Ayurvedic approach. The patient's symptoms include nasal blockage, sneezing, runny nose, and postnasal drip, which can be correlated with kaphaja pratishyaya. Etiological factors such as eating habits, dust exposure and inconsistent sleep led to an aggravation of vata and kapha. The integration of shodhana (nasya karma) and shamana chikitsa effectively targeted both symptom alleviation and the root doshic imbalance. Nasya karma done with anu taila was the key factor in decreasing mucous and enhancing nasal airflow. Internal medications like Haridra Khanda, Sirahsuladi Vajra Rasa, Vyosadi Vati, and Trikatu Churna helped in minimizing kapha buildup, aiding digestion, and restoring doshic balance. Slight modifications in diet and lifestyle also helped to improve the condition & prevent a relapse. The patient was asymptomatic three months after treatment, which highlights the effectiveness of traditional Ayurvedic management in Kaphaja Pratishyaya (Chronic Simple Rhinitis).

CONCLUSION

In this case study, the patient exhibited the classical signs and symptoms of Pratishyaya; through detailed history, the diagnosis of Kaphaja Pratishyaya (Chronic Simple Rhinitis) was confirmed. This case study demonstrates that a combined approach of nidana parivarjan (avoidance of causative factors), nasya, and internal medications is highly effective in the chikitsa of Kaphaja Pratishyaya (Chronic Simple Rhinitis). After three months of treatment, the patient became asymptomatic; therefore, it can be concluded that Ayurvedic chikitsa is effective in the management of Kaphaja Pratishyaya (Chronic Simple Rhinitis).

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